

INCORPORATION OF UNSATURATED POLYESTER BASED MATRIX COMPOSITES INTO A PP-PE COPOLYMER FOR RECYCLING

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SUMMARY: The aim of this research is to recycle waste of unsaturated polyester-based matrix composites reinforced with glass fibres, by grinding and incorporating it into a PP/PE copolymer matrix. Commercial glass fibres were gradually replaced by the ground waste in the composite until complete substitution was attained. Then, the new materials were mechanically tested. Results show a strong decrease in tensile strength and impact resistance. To improve the mechanical properties of composites, the incorporation of an interfacial agent was tested. For this purpose, four different weight contents of an interface agent were introduced. This additive noticeably improves the mechanical results of these new materials. The incorporation of 5% of interfacial agent is found to produce almost the same mechanical results as composites containing only commercial glass fibres.

KEYWORDS: Recycling, unsaturated polyester, glass fibres, calcium carbonate, PP-PE copolymer.

INTRODUCTION

Recycling of unsaturated polyester-based matrix composites reinforced with glass fibres has been a concern since the early 90's. Several treatment techniques have been implemented or are under investigation [1,2]: incineration, chemical treatments [3,4,5], recycling by grinding and incorporation into cement works, civil engineering materials, SMC/BMC or thermoplastics [6,7]. This study deals with recycling through addition to thermoplastics. The matrix selected is a polypropylene.

The aim of this project is to replace partially or totally commercial glass fibres with fibrous waste of glass fibre-polyester composites in a polypropylene, while retaining good mechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Materials

The thermoplastic matrix used is a copolymer PP/PE APPRYL 3150 MN5. Commercial glass fibres are coated for polypropylene and are 3.5 mm long. The polyester composites come from used automobile bumpers. They are composed of three main materials: unsaturated polyester, E glass fibres, and calcium carbonate. These waste products are first ground in order to obtain a fibrous waste, mainly composed of short glass fibres. This product is called AZ1.

Commercial glass fibres were gradually replaced (25% in each step) by the ground waste in the composite until complete substitution was attained. The glass loading (see also table 1) in the composite was kept constant at 20%. In addition, to improve the mechanical properties of these new composites, the incorporation of an interfacial agent in composites,

containing only AZ1, was considered. The compositions of the elaborated materials are shown in table1.

Composites	Loading of PP/PE	Loading of Agent A	Loading of commercial glass fibres	Loading of AZ1	Loading of recycled fibres
PP	100				
FV 20	80		20		
FR5AZ1	76		15	9	5
FR10AZ1	72		10	18	10
FR15AZ1	68		5	27	15
FR20AZ1	64		0	36	20
FR20AZ1-1A	63	1		36	20
FR20AZ1-2A	62	2		36	20
FR20AZ1-3A	61	3		36	20
FR20AZ1-5A	59	5		36	20

Table 1: Composition of materials (% weight)

Methods

Polyester and calcium carbonate contents in the AZ1 were determined by calcination and calcimetry, respectively. The glass fibre content was obtained by calculating the difference.

Composites were first mixed through an extrusion process, then moulded by injection. The apparatus for making compounds is a co-rotative twin screw extruder CLEXTRAL BC21. The total debit was set at 8 kg/h for all compositions. Then, composites were moulded using a 95 ton SANDRETTO Series 8AT. Test pieces were dumb-bell type 1A, in accordance with the ISO 527 specification. A scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL JSM 35CF was used for microstructure observations. Fibre lengths were measured before and after incorporation in polypropylene. In both cases, it was necessary to eliminate the organic phase and calcium carbonate by calcination and reaction with hydrochloric acid, respectively. Then, the cleaned fibres were scattered on a slide. Photographs were taken with a CCD high resolution SONY IRIS camera fixed on a LEICA Laborlux 12 Pol S microscope (X50). The device was connected to a computer. For each specimen, about 1000 fibres were measured to have reproducible results. Measurements were made with image analysis software (IMASYS' OPTIMAS 6.1).

At the time of measurement, corrections have to be carried out. Indeed, only entirely visible fibres are taken into consideration. The longer the fibres are, the more likely they are to cut across the mask of the photograph. To avoid underestimating the population of long fibres, Miles' [8] and Lantuejoul's [9] corrective method was applied. This method which was already used by Averous [10], balances each fibre length with a corrective factor, P.

$$P = \frac{(Z_x - L_x)(Z_y - L_y)}{Z_x Z_y} \quad (1)$$

Z_x and Z_y represent width and length of the mask, respectively, while L_x and L_y represent the X and Y dimensions of the associated rectangle of the fibre (the sides of this rectangle are parallel to the sides of the image). The average number length, the average weight length, and the dispersity factor were calculated. The fibre size distribution of the average number length of AZ1 has been represented.

For a fibre i of corrective factor P_i and size L_i :

Average number length:

$$L_n = \frac{\sum_i \frac{1}{P_i} \times L_i}{\sum_i \frac{1}{P_i}} \quad (2)$$

Average weight length :

$$L_1 = \frac{\sum_i \frac{1}{P_i} \times L_i^2}{\sum_i \frac{1}{P_i} \times L_i} \quad (3)$$

Dispersity factor :

$$D = \frac{L_1 - L_n}{L_n} \quad (4)$$

The following mechanical properties of composites were determined:

- Young's modulus in accordance with ISO 527 specification
- The maximal tensile stress in accordance with ISO 527 specification
- The unnotched and notched Charpy impact resistance in accordance with ISO 179 specification

RESULTS - DISCUSSION

Characterisations of AZ1

The scanning electron micrographs (Fig. 1) show the fibrous nature of AZ1. Some fibres are more or less overlaid by polyester particles containing calcium carbonate inclusions, while others are completely nude (Fig. 1a). Others are stuck together by resin, and form little bundles (Fig. 1b). The presence of many particles of very various sizes made of polyester, calcium carbonate, and particles composed of these two phases is observed.

Fig. 1: Scanning electron micrographs of AZ1

Table 2 shows the composition of AZ1 and the granulometric data of the different components. The fibre size distribution of average number length of fibres of AZ1 is represented in figure 2. AZ1 contains short glass fibres, whose average number length and

weight length are 687 μm and 885 μm , respectively. It is difficult to measure the granulometry of particles of polyester, because they can not be separated from other components. However, scanning electron micrographs show that the spread of particle size is from 10 μm to 400 μm .

Components	% weight	granulometric data
glass fibres	55	$L_n=687 \mu\text{m}$, $L_l=885 \mu\text{m}$, $D=0.28$
Polyester	22.5	range 10 to 400 μm
calcium carbonate	22.5	$d_{50}=2.8 \mu\text{m}$

Table 2 : Composition and granulometric data of the AZ1

Fig. 2: fibre size distribution of the average number length of fibres of AZ1

Mechanical results

The results of mechanical tests (Table 3) show that the replacement of commercial glass fibres by AZ1, without additive, into PP-PE is not very advantageous.

Indeed, the substitution of commercial glass fibres by the ground waste involves a significant reduction of the maximal tensile strength (more than 10% when 25% of fibres are replaced). The composite FR20AZ1 has a maximal tensile strength a little lower than that of the pure matrix. Many explanations of this phenomenon are possible. As the micrograph of fractured surfaces (Fig. 3a) shows, there is a very weak interfacial adhesion between recycled fibres and polypropylene. Similar observations have been made for calcium carbonate or polyester and polypropylene. The contribution of the AZ1 to the tensile strength is weaker than that of the fibres coated for polypropylene. Moreover, the measurements of fibre lengths after injection moulding (Table 4) show that the fibres of AZ1 are shorter than usual fibres. Lastly, it is probable that the presence of very large particles of polyester have a harmful effect on the maximal tensile strength.

The stiffness of composites slightly decreases when AZ1 is introduced, except for in the case of FR20AZ1, in which the value of Young's modulus is a little higher than that of the reference composite FV20. Several parameters are antagonistic. The increase of the global rate of fillers with the rate of substitution should increase the stiffness of composites, but the

recycled fibres are shorter. Furthermore, it is possible that there are some differences in fibre orientation.

Composites	Maximal tensile stress (MPa)	Young's modulus (MPa)	Unnotched impact resistance (kJ/m ²)	Notched impact resistance (kJ/m ²)
PP	26.14 ± 0.12	1370 ± 70	unbroken	6.78 ± 0.30
FV 20	39.21 ± 0.30	3770 ± 95	14.78 ± 0.48	3.10 ± 0.15
FR5AZ1	33.89 ± 0.19	3500 ± 75	13.02 ± 0.58	3.31 ± 0.11
FR10AZ1	30.77 ± 0.18	3560 ± 210	11.84 ± 0.86	3.31 ± 0.24
FR15AZ1	27.30 ± 0.19	3400 ± 90	10.68 ± 0.65	3.35 ± 0.34
FR20AZ1	25.77 ± 0.38	3900 ± 200	10.22 ± 0.99	3.13 ± 0.08
FR20AZ1-1A	31.26 ± 0.22	3520 ± 140	10.04 ± 0.56	6.02 ± 0.78
FR20AZ1-2A	34.58 ± 0.20	3680 ± 130	12.50 ± 1.05	6.00 ± 0.19
FR20AZ1-3A	36.52 ± 0.39	3610 ± 150	15.33 ± 0.71	7.52 ± 0.66
FR20AZ1-5A	38.90 ± 0.30	3770 ± 220	19.25 ± 1.10	8.77 ± 0.70

Table 3 : Mechanical results

As in the case of the maximal tensile strength, the unnotched Charpy impact resistance is clearly diminished when commercial glass fibres are replaced by AZ1. This reduction is essentially due to the large particles of polyester. These particles generate stress concentrations and then favour the initiation of fissures in the material.

The notched impact resistance of composites is not much modified by the introduction of AZ1. The incorporation of AZ1 does not have a great influence on the resistance to the propagation of fissures.

Fig. 3 : Scanning electron micrographs of fractured surfaces of tensile fractured specimens FR20AZ1 (a) and FR20AZ1-5A (b)

The observation of these results lead us to select an appropriate interfacial agent to improve the mechanical properties of composites. This part of the study was done on the composite FR20AZ1. Four different rate were selected: 1%, 2%, 3%, 5% (Table 1).

The incorporation of an interfacial agent appreciably improves the maximal tensile strength of the composite FR20AZ1 (Fig. 4a). When 5% of this additive is added, the composite FR20AZ1-5A has a maximal tensile strength similar to that of the composite FV20. With 3% of interfacial agent incorporated, the strength is just 7% lower than that of the composite of reference. Figure (3b) shows that the agent A makes it possible to create a bonding between fibres and polypropylene. Moreover, it seems that this additive protects the

integrity of fibres. Therefore, it increases the contribution of fibres to the tensile stress. Other scanning electron micrographs have also shown that the incorporation of the interfacial agent A improves the adhesion between calcium carbonate and the matrix.

Figure 4 : Representation of the maximal tensile strength (a), Young's modulus, (b) the unnotched Charpy impact resistance (c) and the notched impact resistance (d) of composite FR20AZ1 as a function of percentage of interfacial agent A

The introduction of the interfacial agent A also strongly improves both unnotched and notched impact resistance of the composite FR20AZ1. For the highest rates of additive, impact resistance is better than those of the composite containing only commercial glass fibres.

	FV20	FR20AZ1	FR20AZ1-3A	FR20AZ1-5A
L_n (μm)	286	198	262	269
L_l (μm)	378	255	344	350
D	0.32	0.28	0.31	0.30

Table 4 : Fibre lengths in composites

CONCLUSION

The recycling of unsaturated polyester based matrix composites reinforced with glass fibres in polypropylene leads to a decrease in the mechanical properties in comparison with commercial glass fibres. However, the incorporation of an appropriate interfacial agent allows commercial glass fibres to be fully replaced by AZ1. This additive clearly improves the interfacial adhesion between AZ1 and polypropylene, and in particular, between, on the one

hand, glass fibres or calcium carbonate, and, on the other hand, the matrix. Furthermore, this interfacial agent seems to protect the integrity of the fibres during the creation of composites.

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